

YOUNG IN CHILDREN ALLERGIC FACTORS TO THE SURFACE EXIT FACTORS

¹Ph.D. Safarov, ²Nasullayev F.O.

¹the head of the x-ray diagnostic department of the Navoi region branch of U.B. RSHTYoM,

²independent researcher

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Allergy is that of the organism some to substances (allergens). The wrong answer to give status Young in children allergic diseases, including asthma, rhinitis, and dermatitis, often occurs. This is the article Young in children allergic factors surface bringer main to factors attention is directed.

1. Genetic factors

For young children allergic to diseases in development genetic factors important role plays If parents in one or two allergies if so, in the child the disease development probability increases. Genetics allergic to reactions predisposition defines and immune system the answer forms.

2. Ecological factors

Ecological conditions, including weather pollution, toxic substances, and allergens, children's allergic reactions caused the release of Urbanization in the process air of quality deterioration, dust, pollen, and other allergens increase children's allergies inclination increases.

3. Nutrition

Nutrition is also allergic to diseases in development important factor is considered It's early in age allergic foods, for example, milk, eggs, and land walnut consumption in children allergic reaction risk increases. Another important factor is that in children probiotic and prebiotic substances are lacking while immune system development negative effects can

4. Infections

Some studies in childhood conducted viral and bacterial infections allergic to diseases' development effects to show possible results. For example, the high breath of the ways infections allergic rhinitis, and asthma development can Immune system to infections relatively The answer is future allergic reactions in defining important have

5. Animals and environment

Children with contact doer animals, especially cats , and dogs, allergic to reactions reason to be in some studies animals with growth in children allergy a risk decrease is showing. This the reason is animals of children are immune to the system useful effect to show an allergen adaptation is to give

6. Psychological factors

Psychological conditions, in particular, stress and anxiety in children allergic reactions strengthen can Stress is immune system function weakens and allergic reactions development can

B and T lymphocytes In children Allergy Importance

B lymphocytes and Allergy

B lymphocytes are allergic in reactions important role plays because they are allergens against antibodies work releases

- **Antibodies answer:** In children, allergic reaction surfaces when it comes, to B cells with allergens after binding, IgE antibodies work to release IgE antibodies allergic symptoms are emitted with cells (for example, mast cells). it is connected while histamine and another chemical substance to release take will come

- **Immune memory:** B cells allergens with the first times when you meet immune memory cells forms. And this with an allergen in the future repeated in touch fast and strong answer to give take it comes in children allergic of symptoms to increase reason to be an

T lymphocytes and Allergy

T lymphocytes, especially T-helper (Th) cells, are allergic in processes important role plays

- **T-helper cells role:** T-helper cells of the Th2 type allergic reactions in strengthening important have They are B lymphocytes IgE antibodies work to issue encourages and allergic the answer manages

- **Immune the answer modulation make :** Th2 cells allergic in reactions important mediators , for example , interleukin-4 (IL-4) and interleukin-13 (IL-13) . work releases These substances B lymphocytes IgE antibodies work to issue allergic symptoms to strengthen encourages.

- **T-regulatory cells:** T-regulatory (Treg) cells immunity in management important role plays They are allergic reactions click and immune system balance to keep help gives In children Treg of cells lack of to allergies inclination to increase can

In children Allergies Development

B and T lymphocytes balance in children allergy in development solution doer important have If T-helper cells are Th2 type active if it is allergic the answer strengthens it while in children allergic diseases, for example, asthma, rhinitis and of dermatitis development take coming can Of this as a result, the organism to allergens against wrong and too much except answer gives

Allergic factors in children to age special meeting	In men	In women
6 months in babies allergy spreading usually around 5-10%. In this period babies have more allergic reactions, for example, food allergies and skin with allergies (for example, eczema). face coming can	5-10%	5-10%
6 years old has been in children allergic to diseases spreading around 20-30 %. During this period children have more allergic diseases, for example, allergic rhinitis, asthma, and food allergies they come	10-20%	5-15%
15 years old has been in children allergic to diseases spreading around 30-40 %. The young in the group children are more allergic to rhinitis, asthma, eczema, and food allergies such as problems with the face they come	30-40%	30-40%

Summary

B and T lymphocytes in children allergic diseases in development important role plays B lymphocytes to allergens against antibodies work secretes, T lymphocytes while immune the answer in management and modulation in doing participation is enough Theirs mutually affect in children allergic reactions in formation important have Immune system right performance and B and T lymphocytes balance in children of allergies prevention get and in treatment main important have

Young children allergic to diseases development one row complicated factors to the effect depend on Genetic predisposition, environmental conditions, nutrition, infections, animals with contact, and psychological factors together children's allergic disease development take will come Theirs an understanding, prevention, and treatment strategies to work on the way out important have

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